

ON $(1, 2)^*$ η -OPEN SETS IN BITOPOLOGICAL SPACES

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Abstract: In this paper, we introduce $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets and obtain the relationships among some existing open sets like $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open, $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open and $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open sets. Also we study some of basic properties of $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets. Further, we introduced $(1, 2)^*$ - η -neighbourhood and discuss some basic properties of $(1, 2)^*$ - η -neighbourhood.

Keywords : $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open, $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open, $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets; $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closure and $(1, 2)^*$ - η -neighbourhood

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1. Introduction

The study of bitopological space was first initiated by Kelly [1] in the year 1963. By using the topological notions, namely, semi-open, regular-open, α -open and pre-open sets, many new bitopological sets are defined and studied by many topologists. In 2008, Ravi et al. [3] studied the notion of $(1, 2)^*$ -open sets in bitopological spaces. In 2004, Ravi and Thivagar [2] studied the concept of stronger form of $(1, 2)^*$ -quotient mapping in bitopological spaces and introduced the concepts of $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open and $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open sets in bitopological spaces. In 2019, Subbulakshmi et al. [5] introduced the concept of η -open sets in topological spaces.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout the paper $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$, (Y, σ_1, σ_2) and (Z, \wp_1, \wp_2) (or simply X , Y and Z) denote bitopological spaces.

Definition 2.1 [2]. Let S be a subset of X . Then S is said to be $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open if $S = A \cup B$, where $A \in \mathfrak{T}_1$ and $B \in \mathfrak{T}_2$. The complement of a $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open set is $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closed.

Definition 2.2 [2]. Let S be a subset of X . Then

- (i) the $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -closure of S , denoted by $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(S)$, is defined as $\bigcap \{F : S \subset F \text{ and } F \text{ is } \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-closed}\}$;
- (ii) the $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -interior of S , denoted by $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(S)$, is defined as $\bigcup \{F : F \subset S \text{ and } F \text{ is } \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-open}\}$.

Note 2.3 [2]. Notice that $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open sets need not necessarily form a topology.

Definition 2.4. A subset A of a bitopological space $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is called

- (i) **regular $(1, 2)^*$ -open** [6] if $A = \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))$,
- (ii) **$(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open** [2] if $A \subset \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(A))$,
- (iii) **$(1, 2)^*$ - α -open** [2] if $A \subset \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(A)))$.

The complement of a $(1, 2)^*$ -regular open (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open, $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open) set is called $(1, 2)^*$ -regular-closed (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed).

The family of all $(1, 2)^*$ -regular-open (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open, $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open) sets in X is denoted by $(1, 2)^*$ -RO(X) (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ -SO(X), $(1, 2)^*$ - α O(X)).

The $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closure (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closure) of a subset A of X is denoted by $(1, 2)^*$ -s-cl(A) (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ - α -cl(A)), defined as the intersection of all $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed. (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed) sets containing A .

Remark 2.5. It is evident that any $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open set of X is a $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open and each $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open set of X is $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open. But the separate converses are not true.

3. $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open sets

Definition 3.1. A subset A of a bitopological space X is said to be **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -open** if $A \subset \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(A))) \cup \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(A))$ and $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed if $A \supset \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))) \cap \mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))$.

The **$(1, 2)^*$ - η -closure** of a subset A of X is denoted by $(1, 2)^*$ - η -cl(A), defined as the intersection of all $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed sets containing A .

The family of all $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ - η -closed) subsets of X is denoted by $(1, 2)^*$ - η O(X) (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ - η C(X)).

Proposition 3.2.

- (i) Every $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open set is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open.
- (ii) Every $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open set is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open.
- (iii) Every regular $(1, 2)^*$ -open set is $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open.
- (iv) Every $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open set is a $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open set.

Proof. (i)

Let A be a $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open set, then

$$A \subset \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A)))$$

$$\Rightarrow A \subset \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A))) \cup \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A))$$

$$\Rightarrow A \text{ is } (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-open set.}$$

Hence A is a $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open set.

(ii) Let A be a $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open set, then

$$A \subset \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A))$$

$$\Rightarrow A \subset \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A)) \cup \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A)))$$

or

$$A \subset \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A))) \cup \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A))$$

$$\Rightarrow A \text{ is } (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-open set.}$$

Hence A is a $(1, 2)^*$ - η -open set.

(iii) Let A be a $(1, 2)^*$ -regular open set, then

$$A = \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(A)) \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

$$\Rightarrow \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A) = \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(A)))$$

$$\Rightarrow \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A) = \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A))$$

Using (i)

$$\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A) = A \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

Hence A is $\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2$ -open.

Now we know that

$$A \subset \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(A)$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{int}(A) \subset \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(A))$$

Using (ii)

$$A \subset \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(A))$$

Again using (ii), we get

$$A \subset \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A)))$$

$$\Rightarrow A \subset \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A))) \cup \mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-cl}(\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2\text{-int}(A))$$

Hence, A is $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open set.

(iv) East to prove.

Remark 3.3. We have the following implications for the properties of subsets:

$$\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}\text{-open} \Rightarrow (1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha\text{-open} \Rightarrow (1, 2)^*\text{-semi-open} \Rightarrow (1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-open}$$

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, \{b\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$. Then

(i) The $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open sets are : $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, X$.

(ii) The $(1, 2)^*\text{-semi-open}$ sets are : $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X$.

(iii) The $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha$ -open sets are : $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X$

(iv) The $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open sets are : $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X$.

Example 3.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, \{b\}, X\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, \{c\}, X\}$. Then

(i) The $\mathfrak{T}_{1,2}$ -open sets are : $\phi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, X$.

(ii) The $(1, 2)^*\text{-semi-open}$ sets are : $\phi, X, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.

(iii) The $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha$ -open sets are : $\phi, X, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}$.

(iv) The $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open sets are : $\phi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X$.

Example 3.6. Let $X = \{a, b, c, \}$, $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, \{b\}, X\}$. Then

(i) The $\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2$ -open sets are : $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X$.

(ii) The $(1, 2)^*\text{-semi-open}$ sets are : $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X$.

(iii) The $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha$ -open sets are : $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X$.

(iv) The $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open sets are : $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X$.

Example 3.7. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$.

Then

(i) The $\mathfrak{T}_1\mathfrak{T}_2$ -open sets are : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(ii) The $(1, 2)^*\text{-semi-open}$ sets are : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(iii) The $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha$ -open sets are : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(iv) The $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open sets are : $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

Theorem 3.8. Intersection of two $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open sets need not be a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open set.

Proof. East to verify.

Example 3.9. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$. Then $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{O}(X) = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$. Here $A = \{c, d\}$ and $B = \{a, b, d\}$ are $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open sets, but $A \cap B = \{d\}$ is not a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open set.

Theorem 3.9. The finite union of $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ open sets is a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ open set.

Proof. Easy to verify.

4. $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -neighborhood and their basic properties

In this section, we introduce $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -neighborhood (shortly $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd in bitopological spaces by using the notion of $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open sets. We prove that every nbhd of x in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd of x but not conversely.

Definition 4.1. Let $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ be a bitopological space and let $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. A subset N of $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is said to be a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd of x iff there exists a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$.

Definition 4.2. A subset N of a bitopological space $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$, is called a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd of $A \subset (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ iff there exists a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open set G such that $A \subset G \subset N$.

Remark 4.3. The $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd N of $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ need not be a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$.

Example 4.4. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{O}(X) = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$. Note that $\{a, d\}$ is not a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open set, but it is a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd of a , since $\{a\}$ is a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open set such that $a \in \{a\} \subset \{a, d\}$.

Theorem 4.5. Every nbhd N of $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd of $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$.

Proof. Let N be a nbhd of point $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. To prove that N is a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd of x . By definition of nbhd, there exists an open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$. As every open set is $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open set so, G is $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open set such that $x \in G \subset N$. Hence N is $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd of x .

Remark 4.6. In general, a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd N of $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ need not be a nbhd of x in $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$, as seen from the following example.

Example 4.7. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with topology $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_2 = \{\phi, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Then $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{O}(X) = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$. The set $\{a, c\}$ is $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd of the point c , since the $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open set $\{a, c\}$ is such that $c \in \{a, c\} \subset \{a, c\}$. However, the set $\{a, c\}$ is not a nbhd of the point c , since no open set G exists such that $c \in G \subset \{a, c\}$.

Theorem 4.8. If a subset N of a space $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open, then N is a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd of each of its points.

Proof. Suppose N is $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open. Let $x \in N$. We claim that N is $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd of x . For N is a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -open set such that $x \in N \subset N$. Since x is an arbitrary point of N , it follows that N is a $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd of each of its points.

Definition 4.9. Let x be a point in a space $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. The set of all $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd of x is called the $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhd system at x , and is denoted by $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-N}(x)$.

Theorem 4.10. Let $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ be a bitopological space and for each $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. Let $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-N}(x)$ be the collection of all $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta$ -nbhds of x . Then we have the following results.

(i) $\forall x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$, $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\eta\text{-N}(x) \neq \phi$.

(ii) $N \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x) \Rightarrow x \in N$.

(iii) $N \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x), M \supset N \Rightarrow M \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x)$.

(iv) $N \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x), M \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x) \Rightarrow N \cap M \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x)$.

(v) $N \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x) \Rightarrow$ there exists $M \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x)$ such that $M \subset N$ and $M \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(y)$ for every $y \in M$.

Proof. (i) Since $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is a $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -open set, it is a $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -nbhd of every $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. Hence there exists at least one $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -nbhd (namely - $(X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$) for each $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$. Hence $(1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x) \neq \phi$ for every $x \in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, \mathfrak{T}_2)$.

(ii) If $N \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x)$, then N is a $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -nbhd of x . So by definition of $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -nbhd, $x \in N$.

(iii) Let $N \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x)$ and $M \supset N$. Then there is a $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$. Since $N \subset M$, $x \in G \subset M$ and so M is $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -nbhd of x . Hence $M \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x)$.

(iv) Let $N \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x)$ and $M \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x)$. Then by definition of $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -nbhd. Hence $x \in G_1 \cap G_2 \subset N \cap M \Rightarrow (1)$. Since $G_1 \cap G_2$ is a $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -open set, (being the intersection of two $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -open sets), it follows from (1) that $N \cap M$ is a $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -nbhd of x . Hence $N \cap M \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x)$.

(v) If $N \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(x)$, then there exists a $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -open set M such that $x \in M \subset N$. Since M is a $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -open set, it is $(1, 2)^*-\eta$ -nbhd of each of its points. Therefore $M \in (1, 2)^*-\eta-N(y)$ for every $y \in M$.

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